

SUPERSHINE

D4.3: Action Plan for the Lighthouse Districts – Part 1

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1. Executive summary

This document outlines the action plan for the implementation of EE interventions in the SUPERSHINE lighthouses, focusing on technical, financial, social, and environmental aspects. It also introduces the concept of a one-stop shop to streamline the renovation process and maximise benefits.

The technical aspects of the plan include comprehensive energy efficiency interventions such as improved insulation, advanced heating systems, and energy-efficient windows. These measures aim to significantly reduce energy consumption and enhance overall building performance. The renovation process is structured over multiple phases to ensure minimal disruption to residents while achieving technical upgrades efficiently.

From a financial perspective, the total investment plan for the renovation projects provides detailed breakdowns for initial investments, operating, and maintenance expenses. Investments are distributed over several periods to manage cash flow and ensure financial feasibility. The funding structure involves a mix of contributions from residents, municipal guarantees, and support from national and local funding institutions. Innovative financial models such as public-private partnerships (PPPs) and energy performance contracting are employed to ensure financial viability. Post-renovation, the involved buildings are expected to see an increase in market value, and revenues from rent and other sources are projected to rise, contributing to the financial sustainability of the projects. The public-private partnerships (PPPs) leverage collaboration with the private sector to pool resources and expertise from both public and private sectors. This collaboration aims to share risks and benefits, ensuring that both parties have a vested interest in the success of the projects. Private entities may provide funding, technical expertise, and operational support, while public entities offer regulatory support, guarantees, and additional financing mechanisms. Under the guaranteed savings model, the social housing company covers initial costs via savings, grants, and funding institutions, while an Energy Service Company (ESCO) handles installation, maintenance, and operational costs. A minimum level of energy savings is guaranteed, with financial risks borne by the ESCO. In the shared savings model, the ESCO funds the energy efficiency interventions, bearing the costs of operation and maintenance. The social housing company provides the capital asset and is guaranteed a minimum level of energy savings.

Socially, the renovations aim to enhance the quality of life for residents by providing better housing standards and reducing energy costs. Efforts are made to ensure housing remains affordable, with minimal rent increases and maintenance of social housing benefits. By improving energy efficiency,

the projects aim to lower the proportion of income spent on energy by households, addressing energy poverty and ensuring homes are adequately warm.

Environmentally, the technical interventions are expected to result in significant energy savings and a reduction in CO2 emissions. Projected annual energy savings include substantial reductions in both electricity and heating consumption. The plan promotes sustainable building practices and the use of eco-friendly materials, aligning with broader environmental goals and contributing to climate change mitigation.

The establishment of the SUPERSHINE one-stop shop will offer a streamlined approach to building renovations, providing residents and stakeholders with a single point of contact for all renovation-related services. This includes project planning, financing options, technical assessments, and execution. By consolidating services, the one-stop shop aims to reduce complexity, enhance coordination, and improve the overall efficiency of the renovation process. This model ensures that all aspects of a renovation project are managed cohesively, from initial consultation to final implementation.

1.1 Goal of the document

The primary objective of this document is to outline the implementation of SUPERSHINE solutions and initial technology in various lighthouse districts. This is part of Task 4.2, which follows the feasibility studies developed in Task 4.1.

The main outcome of this task will be a SUPERSHINE solutions implementation plan for each lighthouse park. These plans will present viable medium-term options for investments in energy-related solutions, evaluated based on social, cost, environmental, and financial key performance indicators (KPIs). The social housing management, with support from scientific partners, will elaborate these plans.

In addition to the implementation strategies, the plans will also address the barriers encountered during the process. Assessments of how these barriers can be overcome in the specific context of each lighthouse district will be included.

The document will also present Deliverable D4.3 – an action plan for the lighthouse districts. This action plan will guide the lighthouse districts through the implementation phase, offering viable

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medium-term options for investments in energy-related solutions. The targets of this report will be social housing management.

The report will host the KPIs Assessment, the Initial Technology radar, and validated bottom-up business models. It will also include a comprehensive action plan that considers all aspects - technical, environmental, financial, and social. This holistic approach will help identify any restrictions or barriers that could affect the SUPERSHINE action plan in each of the lighthouse districts in Denmark, Latvia, and Italy.

The steps involved in this process include gathering necessary information for triple analysis, creating KPIs for implementation, and preparing an Action Plan that includes the One Stop Shop as a tool to facilitate renovation. This comprehensive approach ensures that all aspects are considered, leading to a more effective and efficient implementation of the SUPERSHINE solutions.

Finally, the social engagement and social innovation actions outlined for each SUPERSHINE lighthouse city as detailed in the engagement strategy document (D1.2). These actions are grouped by city and structured to align with the timeline and impact goals of the project:

1. Technical requirements prior to retrofit interventions and Implementation in the lighthouses

2.1 Denmark

2.1.1 Technical Specifications

The municipality of Herning, with 89,000 residents, is in Midtjylland and aims to be CO2-neutral in 2030 using renewable energy. The FællesBo district, which includes a residential area and a big shopping centre, has ICT services, fibre optic connections, and the Neogrid energy management system.

In 2015, it emitted 365,000 tons of CO2, mainly from transportation. Herning uses a biomass and solar heating system, with the Herningværket plant providing heat to 48,000 homes. Local Plans support sustainability and mobility, including charging stations for electric vehicles, recycling, and local renewable energy production. FællesBo plans to install solar panels on four buildings and is considering establishing an energy community after overcoming regulatory and funding barriers.

The representative building in Department 16 of FællesBo, part of five blocks built in 1958 and renovated in 1984 and 1996, is undergoing major renovations to improve energy efficiency, cutting annual consumption from 147 kWh/m² to 78 kWh/m². Upgrades include biomass heating, LED lighting, solar panels, and structural and interior renovations. Most tenants are low-income, with 68% living alone, 26% over 60, and 20% immigrants. Half have no formal education, and 53% are employed. These improvements aim to reduce energy bills and enhance the health and quality of life for these residents.

Department 16					Department 19				
Block	Floor	Apartment	Energy Consumption		Block	Floor	Apartment	Energy Consumption	
			Before renovation	After renovation				Before renovation	After renovation
5	4	89	224,88 kWh/m ²	64,70 kWh/m ²	6	3	210	224,05 kWh/m ²	79,50 kWh/m ²
Renovation Period					Renovation Period				
April 2023			October 2024		June 2024			May 2028	

Department 21					Department 24				
Block	Floor	Apartment	Energy Consumption		Block	Floor	Apartment	Energy Consumption	
			Before renovation	After renovation				Before renovation	After renovation
3	3	123	199,56 kWh/m ²	69,90 kWh/m ²	11	3	270	241,46 kWh/m ²	132,90 kWh/m ²
Renovation Period					Renovation Period				
October 2023			September 2026		July 2022			December 2025	

The renovation project will significantly improve the comfort and health conditions of the homes, as well as reduce energy and water consumption. The apartments outside the SUPERSHINE pilot area, such as apartment 104, will also be renovated with an additional budget of 1,906 million DKK (254.1 million EUR). In the area, some rehabilitation actions will be improved, which are included in the following list:

- **Insulation** of exterior walls, basements, and roofs.
- The main focus of FællesBo's renovation **project is recycling and waste** minimization. Seven general departments, including departments 16, 19, 21, and 24, are being renovated, with nearly 2,000 homes to be renovated over the next 6-8 years. A collaboration has been established with the company Next to map recyclable materials and with Titan Nedbrydning to build a greenhouse using recycled materials.
- Balanced **mechanical ventilation systems**.
- FællesBo will implement **new water and electricity installations**, including electric charging stations in all its departments, including departments 16, 19, 21, and 24. Despite the low initial demand detected in a survey, it is believed that this is due to the lack of existing stations. An external provider will install the stations, and the costs will be covered by the residents through the charging price. Currently, offers from three different providers are being evaluated.
- **LED lighting** in common areas.
- **Electronic thermostats** (all radiators).
- FællesBo, as a **social housing company**, develops renovation plans in conjunction with tenant boards, expert consultants in building renovation, and financial support from Landsbyggefonden.

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- FællesBo will **integrate photovoltaic systems** into the buildings of departments 16, 19, 21, and 24 within the SUPERSHINE project, in addition to departments 104, 106, and 107. Henrik Bielefeldt from SUSTAIN proposes to install and finance solar cells in department 16, while FællesBo will establish solar systems and discuss financing with Sydbank for departments 19, 21, and 24.
- FællesBo is working to incorporate more **wild nature** and meadow flowers into their plans, combined with rainwater beds. A request to the Nordea Foundation has been approved to establish a **green and blue oasis** in the Holtbjerg area. Additionally, FællesBo is participating in a network facilitated by Bæredygtig Herning to gain **inspiration on biodiversity**.

2.1.2 Legal

Management structure of the implementations

For building renovation FællesBo (FB) Social Housing Company as the owner carries out a tendering process for selecting the company to carry out the renovation. FællesBo has a building owner and a consulting company to carry out supervision of the renovation.

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Procurement processes, selection of contractors

For SUPERSHINE's development activities, direct contracts have been established with suppliers without undergoing a tendering process. Specifically, for energy management activities, a supplier for the energy management system was contracted directly. Similarly, for recycling/use activities and rewilding activities, contracts were made with suppliers for the energy management system without a tendering process. Additionally, for PV activities, a contract was made directly with a supplier for the PV system, as the amount involved fell below the threshold that mandates a tendering process. This approach ensures streamlined procurement and timely project implementation.

Risk management and preventive, corrective actions

For building renovation projects, the winner of the tender is responsible for executing the renovation in accordance with the contract, thereby managing risks related to timing, contracting, materials used, and implementation difficulties. In the case of SUPERSHINE's energy management, PV, recycling/use, and rewilding activities, direct contracts have been established with companies delivering the services. This ensures that each service provider is accountable for adhering to the contractual terms and managing the associated risks efficiently.

Implementation plan

The Danish implementation plan focuses on integrating innovative solutions to enhance sustainability and energy efficiency in building environments. The key activities include installing photovoltaic panels and battery packages for renewable energy, developing advanced energy (heat) management systems, promoting biodiversity, and facilitating the reuse and recycling of building materials. These initiatives are designed to create a greener and more resilient built environment in Denmark. The timeline below outlines the schedule for implementing these activities.

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DENMARK		2023												2024											
Actions		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
PV + Battery packages	Cooperation with SUSTAIN regarding the project. Below: - Integrating solar cells for department 16, Covering how the investment can be financed, Resident management																								
	Approval of the project with solar cells at a departmental meeting in dept. 16																								
	Choice of financing via Sydbank instead of PKA via SUSTAIN (department 16)																								
	Installation of solar cell system, department 16, stage 1																								
	Installation of solar cell system, department 15 stage 2																								
	Framework agreement on the tender of solar cell systems																								
	Selection of supplier of solar cell systems																								
	Finding out how the investment can be financed via savings on the electricity bill.																								
	Approval of the project with solar cells at dept. 21																								
	Approval of the project with solar cells at dept. 24																								
	Installation of solar systems in both departments begins																								
	Energy (heat) management	Uncovering how to work systematically with heat management in FællesBo's departments in order to achieve savings on the heating bill for the residents.																							
Meeting with the Craftsman Department at FællesBo regarding systematic heat management																									
Selection of case departments for heat management																									
Biodiversity	Departments in FællesBo where biodiversity is being worked on.																								
	Calculation is operating savings for flower meadows and mowing plus dissemination of the message.																								
	Evening meeting with all department boards in FællesBo regarding biodiversity																								
	Case project regarding biodiversity incl. dissemination of the good effects of biodiversity solutions on outdoor areas																								
Reuse and Recycling of building materials	Mini-resource mapping of possible recycled wood in FællesBo's departments																								
	Study of a model for renting out sheds to FællesBo from own recycled wood																								
	Use of timber from FællesBos dept. 104 for garden shed and firehouse																								
	Construction of an orangery of recycled materials from department																								

2.1.3 Economic

Collecting specific financial information

According to FaellsBo housing association the key stakeholders involved in the energy efficiency renovation process are the tenants of FaellesBo district, local building renovation expert companies, the municipality of Herning, Landsbyggefonden funding institution, and local ESCOs carrying out the renewable energy sources renovations. The planned energy efficiency refurbishment in the FaellesBo district is intended to increase energy efficiency of the public lighting system, energy efficiency of the water network, installing renewable energy systems such as the FællesBo PV systems, and improving the mobility system such as establishing EV charging stations. Furthermore, FaellesBo social housing is teaming up with local business and ESCOs to develop PPPs and crowdfunding schemes for financing the installation of the planned energy efficiency renovations.

Based on the estimates from FaellsBo housing association, the initial investment costs required to implement the proposed energy efficiency interventions for department 16, is 1,174,201 million EUR. The expected investment cost will be covered by several stakeholders, where residents will cover 2% of the investment costs, 10%-12% will be covered by municipal guarantees, and the rest will be covered by Landsbyggefonden funding institutions. Currently, the residents have deposited 100,00 EUR.

Prior to the energy efficiency renovations, residents of FællesBo Department 16 consumed an average of 147 kWh/m² per year for heating, costing 743 EUR/kWh annually. This translates to approximately 130 EUR/m² per household per year. The residents in FællesBo Department 16 are categorised into three groups based on income and family size:

- A single-person household on social welfare earns about 25,000 EUR per year.
- A two-person household with one person working earns about 40,000 EUR per year.
- A two-person household with both partners working earns about 70,000 EUR per year.

As a result, the percentage of annual heat consumption cost relative to the household's annual income ranges from 1.5% to 4%, depending on the income band.

Additionally, residents consume an average of 2000 kWh per year in electricity. The percentage of annual electricity consumption cost relative to household income ranges from 1.8% to 5.2%, again depending on the income band. Furthermore, the FællesBo social housing company estimates that 20% of the households they manage are unable to keep their homes adequately warm. During the

energy efficiency renovation period, current inhabitants will be relocated to other nearby social housing units within the FællesBo district.

Main outcomes

Investment Costs: the renovation costs for energy measures in Department 16 total 1,174,201 EUR. This encompasses start-up costs, as the building renovation is a turnkey delivery. The annual capital spend is distributed over two periods: 556,200 EUR from April 2023 (spanning nine months) and 618,000 EUR from October 2024 (spanning ten months). While the primary focus of the renovation is on improving housing standards rather than energy savings alone, the payback period based on energy savings is estimated at 26 years. The total energy savings are projected to be 45,631 EUR per year, with electricity savings accounting for 14,765 EUR (55,000 kWh/year) and heating savings amounting to 30,856 EUR (451,000 kWh/year).

Operating and Maintenance Costs: the annual operating and maintenance costs are estimated at 700,000 EUR. Depreciation rates for the renovated building components are as follows: walls insulated with 190 mm rockwool have a depreciation rate of 3.3%, the roof insulated with 400 mm rockwool granulate also has a depreciation rate of 3.3%, and the 3-layer low energy windows have a depreciation rate of 5%. The expected lifespan of these components is 30 years for the walls and roof, and 20 years for the windows.

Revenues and Taxes: the project expects a 3% annual increase in rent. The tax rate on rents collected from social housing buildings is 3%, and the real estate tax amounts to 21,208 EUR. However, there are no tax incentives available for carrying out the energy efficiency refurbishments. Rent payments from tenants in Department 16 amount to 657,800 EUR/year, with the average apartment rent being 7,400 EUR/year.

Funding and Debt: the funding structure for the renovation of Department 16 relies on resident deposits, which amount to 100,000 EUR. In the Danish social housing finance system, equity is represented by resident deposits, as there is no traditional equity structure. Additionally, there are existing mortgage loans without public support, with a 2.9% interest rate, totalling 622,754 EUR before the renovation.

Market Value of the building and energy poverty: after the renovation, the expected market value of the buildings is estimated to be between 9 and 15 million EUR. Energy expenditure for the year 2023, before the renovation, is calculated as follows: heat consumption costs 5,545 DKK/year (747 EUR/year), with an additional fixed payment of 1,138 DKK/year (153 EUR/year), totalling 1,023

EUR/year. The proportion of income spent on energy varies by wage band. For a single person household on social welfare (earning around 25,000 EUR/year), the cost is 4% of their annual income. For a lower middle-class household with one person working (earning around 40,000 EUR/year), the cost is 2.5%, and for a dual-income household (earning 70-80,000 EUR/year), the cost ranges from 1.2% to 1.5%. Including electricity consumption, these percentages rise to 5.2%, 3.3%, and 1.8% respectively. In department 16 around 20% of households managed by FællesBo are unable to keep their homes adequately warm, which reflects the broader issue of energy poverty in the district.

Possible financial solutions and steps for evaluating them

Based on the information provided by FaellsBo housing association for Herning department 16, we have identified key characteristics to be considered when developing the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) contracts and the **crowdfunding** scheme.

- The social housing stock in Denmark is entirely owned by social housing companies, ensuring centralized management and oversight.
- Tenants will benefit directly from the energy efficiency (EE) renovations, as they will receive a portion of the energy savings generated. Additionally, tenants are expected to cover 2% of the investment costs for these renovations, reflecting their stake in the improvements.
- The rent paid by tenants is directed to the national building fund, contributing to the overall sustainability and maintenance of the housing stock. The government also stands to benefit significantly from these renovations, as reduced CO2 emissions align with national environmental goals.
- Local funding institutions are set to receive a share of the financial benefits resulting from the energy savings, creating a mutually beneficial arrangement for all parties involved.

The financial solutions which will be analysed are:

1. Guaranteed savings: in Denmark the social housing company will cover the initial investment costs through savings, grants, crowdfunding and funding institutions, while the ESCO is responsible for the installation, maintenance and operation costs of the EE interventions. The social housing company is guaranteed a minimum level of energy savings equal to the cost of financing the EE interventions. If the annual energy savings are below the minimum guaranteed level the ESCO company pays the difference to the social housing company, however when the annual energy savings are higher than the minimum guaranteed level the social housing company receives the minimum guaranteed savings plus 20% of the difference between the annual energy savings and the minimum guaranteed

level. Usually the duration of this contract is 20 years, and the financial and technical risks are covered by the ESCO.

2. **Shared savings**: the ESCO is responsible for funding the EE intervention and the operating and maintenance costs while the social housing company provides the capital asset. The ESCO is guaranteed a minimum level of energy savings equal to its annual costs. If the annual energy savings are below the minimum guaranteed level, the ESCO will receive all the energy savings and the social housing company receives 0. In the case the annual energy savings are higher than the minimum guaranteed for the ESCO, the ESCO will receive the minimum guaranteed level of energy savings + 60% of the difference between the annual energy savings and the guaranteed minimum energy savings, while the social housing company receives the rest. The financial risk is covered by the ESCO, and the duration of these contracts are usually between 20-25 years.
3. **Direct credit line**: the Social housing company is responsible for funding the EE project, and covering the maintenance and operating costs of implementing the EE interventions. The financial risk and technical risk are covered by the Social housing company.
4. **Energy supply contracts**: the social housing company and the ESCO both cover the investment costs of the EE renovation project usually at a rate of 10%-50% for the social housing company. No party is guaranteed a minimum energy savings level, and the annual energy savings are divided according to the percentage covered by each party. The financial risk and technical risk are also shared between the parties according to the percentage of initial investments covered by each party.

2.1.4 Social

Health and Safety Measures on site

During implementation, robust Danish health and safety measures, overseen by the Danish Working Environment Authority (Arbejdstilsynet), will be strictly followed for the workforce. The Working Environment Act (Arbejds miljøloven) governs health and safety at work, outlining the responsibilities of employers, employees, and authorities. Key measures include:

- **Risk Assessment:** Conducting regular workplace risk assessments to identify hazards and implement measures to mitigate them.
- **Workplace Instructions:** Providing employees with clear instructions and training on safe work practices and procedures.

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- **Health and Safety Organization:** Establishing a health and safety organisation within the workplace, which includes appointing safety representatives and forming safety committees in larger workplaces.
- **Preventive Measures:** Implementing preventive measures to address identified risks, including providing necessary protective equipment and ensuring safe work conditions.

For building renovation projects, tenants will be re-housed in other buildings to ensure their safety. For the four SUPERSHINE activities—energy management, PV, recycling/use, and rewilding—there are no health and safety issues affecting the tenants. This comprehensive approach ensures both worker safety and tenant well-being throughout the project implementation.

Social engagement & social innovation actions in Herning Denmark

In Herning, Denmark, the social engagement actions leverage the country's tenant democracy model, a cornerstone of Danish housing policy, to ensure residents are active decision-makers throughout every stage of the renovation process. This model fosters and facilitates participatory governance by involving tenant boards, who not only approve but also influence the design and implementation of renovation activities. This collaborative framework builds awareness, trust and aligns community needs with sustainability goals.

The awareness and launch phase, which began in late 2023, employs tenant meetings and surveys to build support and gather insights from the community. These efforts lay the groundwork for an inclusive and well-informed renovation journey. Moving into the design and renovation phases, the project introduces thematic workshops focused on key sustainability pillars: : renewable energy systems, energy management, biodiversity rewilding, and material recycling. Residents participate alongside municipal authorities, local businesses, and sustainability experts to co-develop solutions tailored to the community's unique context. This partnership approach transforms residents from passive recipients into proactive contributors to the neighbourhood's transformation..

Post-renovation activities will focus on embedding sustainable practices into daily life, offering practical sessions to guide residents on efficient energy use, waste management, and material recycling techniques. These sessions aim to cement long-term behavioural changes, ensuring the renovations deliver lasting environmental and social benefits. .

The project's social innovation phased timeline, running from late 2023 through 2026, is designed to sustain engagement, providing ample time for tailored capacity-building programmes. These programmes not only educate but also empower tenants to take ownership of their improved living environment.

The project's innovation and engagement phased timeline, running from late 2023 through 2026, is designed to sustain engagement, providing ample time for tailored capacity-building programmes. These programmes not only educate but also empower tenants to take ownership of their improved

living environment. By integrating social engagement with cutting-edge sustainable solutions, ensuring sustained involvement and tailored capacity-building programs.

2.1.5 Environmental

Waste management

In Denmark, the Danish Environmental Protection Act regulates environmental protection and waste management practices. It mandates that specific hazardous materials, such as PCB and thermo-windows, generated during building renovations, must be treated as hazardous waste. Under the Waste Act, companies are required to sort waste fractions like natural stone (e.g., granite and flint), unglazed tiles (brick and roof tiles), concrete, mixtures of natural stone, unglazed brick, and concrete, iron and metal, cast, stone wool, land, asphalt, and mixtures of concrete and asphalt for proper disposal. Companies have the option to send unsorted construction waste to registered sorting facilities. If the amount of waste generated does not exceed 1 ton, companies may choose not to sort at the source, with the responsibility falling to the municipality to ensure proper sorting and disposal.

Carbon management of site activities (if any)

There is no DK regulation on carbon management related to building renovation.

Biodiversity impact of the implementations

Building renovation activities cause temporary disturbances to local wildlife, including birds and insects that inhabit nearby green areas. However, these activities contribute to long-term biodiversity conservation through reduced energy consumption and increased use of renewable energy sources, which mitigate CO₂ emissions.

Additionally, the implementation of rewilding activities under the 4 SUPERSHINE lines of action directly enhances biodiversity. This includes initiatives aimed at restoring natural habitats, resulting in improvements for various species including plants, insects, birds, hedgehogs, and other wildlife. Thus, while renovations may pose short-term challenges for local fauna, the overall impact supports sustainable practices that benefit biodiversity in the long run.

2.2 Latvia

2.2.1 Technical Specifications

The district Priedes offers a variety of services but the municipality acknowledges the need to improve public transportation during weekends and to create a café and a youth centre. The area is included in the Riga Sustainable Development Program (2021-2027), which promotes sustainable mobility and the implementation of various renovation strategies. The district also has land available for new infrastructure and renewable energy generation, as well as the connection of all homes to high-speed internet and 5G services.

The Āgenskalna Priedes district has access to the city's DH. The buildings in the district are connected to Riga's municipal heating network and are equipped with automatic heat exchange units based on the outside temperature. The DH features a cogeneration system using natural gas and biomass, with 41% of the energy coming from renewable sources, although the systems it has are old and inefficient. The city of Riga is committed to decarbonization, planning to integrate renewable energy technologies and improve the efficiency of the heating network.

The district faces heat losses of 10.0-10.5% and lacks shared energy production systems or energy communities. The barriers to urban regeneration include the fragmentation of land ownership and the lack of interest from private investors. Investment plans focused on improving energy efficiency, mobility, and digitalization are being promoted.

The buildings in the Āgenskalna Priedes district, known as "Hruschovka," are multi-apartment buildings of the 316 series, constructed between 1960 and 1961, with a capacity of 40 to 60 apartments per building. The buildings are predominantly privately owned, although they are managed by the municipal company *Rīgas namu pārvaldnieks* (RNP). Each building, located on a plot of 350 to 600 m², has a centralised heating and hot water system, powered by natural gas and biomass, with no on-site renewable energy production. The average heating energy consumption of the buildings is 223 kWh/m² per year, although renovations are expected to reduce energy consumption by 60%, generating annual savings of 30,000 EUR per building.

Renovation Actions

Shift from a single-building renovation approach to an integrated neighbourhood renovation approach: a comprehensive strategy that, besides focusing on buildings, also emphasises sustainability and climate change adaptation, clean mobility, the advantages of digital technologies, health, well-being, etc. Promote energy retrofits (decisions must be made by the residents of each pilot site building separately), although it is expected to include wall and roof insulation, improved

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heating and ventilation systems, and the possible installation of solar panels. In addition to building renovation, energy performance contracts for buildings and ESCOs (Energy Service Companies) will be used to accelerate the pace of building renovation and the available resources.

Energy Management

Establish citizen energy communities (CEs) driven by the municipality with the aim of reducing energy poverty.

Financial Resources

CEs will be used as an instrument to combat energy poverty and funding options will be diversified, and additional funds will be mobilised, for example, in the form of green bonds.

2.2.2 Legal

Management structure of the implementations

In Riga, the management of interventions, particularly for the renovation of multi-apartment buildings, involves several steps and key stakeholders. Typically, the process is initiated by the apartment owners, who play a central role in deciding how the project will be managed. The apartment owners usually hire a project manager to oversee the renovation. This can be done directly through a collective vote or through their legal body, such as a house owner's association,

if one exists. If a house owner's association is involved, they must have a mandate given by a vote from the apartment owners to act on their behalf.

The project management service is often provided by the building's management company. For instance, in our pilot project, this role is fulfilled by SIA "Rīgas namu pārvaldnieks" (RNP). However, the project management can also be handled by the construction company responsible for the renovation work. In some cases, though less common, the house owner's association itself can act as the project manager, managing the renovation project directly.

Once a project manager is appointed, their responsibilities include sourcing and coordinating other service providers required for the renovation. The project manager ensures that all aspects of the renovation are carried out efficiently and in accordance with the agreed-upon plans and regulations.

Procurement processes, selection of contractors

The selection of contractors and procurement processes are managed by the project manager, who could be from the housing management company, a construction company, or the homeowners association. These decisions are then approved through a vote by the apartment owners.

However, there are instances where the building documentation for the planned intervention is completed before a project manager is even contracted. This can occur if the apartment owners take the initiative to prepare the documentation themselves or if the building's management company completes this task as part of their standard housing management duties, independent of any specific project management arrangement.

In such cases, it is quite common for the apartment owners to take the next step by conducting their own market research. They seek out and evaluate potential construction companies that can provide a comprehensive package, including both project management services and the actual brick-and-mortar construction work.

Risk management and preventive, corrective actions

Risk management is primarily the responsibility of the project manager. To mitigate risks, especially related to construction, it is crucial to incorporate measures into contracts with all involved parties to safeguard against price increases that could render the project unviable. For instance, contracts should ensure that construction companies can complete the project within the agreed budget, despite any potential cost escalations.

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Laws mandate that an independent energy efficiency specialist must provide recommendations on suitable materials. Additionally, the architect is responsible for the technical aspects of the project, using their qualifications to ensure accuracy and feasibility. A construction site supervisor is essential for overseeing the work, and another designated party must ensure that the technical project criteria are precisely followed throughout implementation.

Implementation plan

This implementation plan for Latvia includes key activities to improve energy efficiency in residential buildings. The steps are: engaging inhabitants, obtaining initial and final decisions from apartment owners, applying to co-financing schemes, tendering for and developing technical documentation, registering a homeowners association, getting construction board approval, tendering for a construction company, signing contracts, executing construction works, and preparing an evaluation report.

Project stage	No. of weeks (approx.)	Pre-project stage	1st year				2nd year				3rd year			
Preparatory work with inhabitants	12													
1st apartment owner decision	4													
Application to co-financing scheme ALTUM	4													
Tenders for technical documentation	4													
Pre-application to co-financing scheme ALTUM	4													
Registration of a home-owners association	4													
Communication with the housing manager	4													
Work on technical documentation, approval from construction board	54													
ALTUM evaluation of technical documentation	4													
Tender for construction company	8													
ALTUM evaluation of tenders	4													
Final application to co-financing scheme ALTUM and 2nd apartment owner decision (i.e. vote)	10													
Communication with the housing manager	4													
Signing of contracts	4													
Construction works	52													
Evaluation report	6													

4.2.3 Economic

Collecting specific financial information from the lighthouses and main outcomes

Investment Costs: the total investment cost for implementing the proposed EE renovations is €318,000 per building in 2023. This rise is driven by the scarcity of building materials from the Russian, Ukrainian, and Belarusian markets due to ongoing conflicts and sanctions, compounded by the global energy crisis. Given the standard design of these buildings, constructed primarily in the 1960s and managed by LLC “Rīgas namu pārvaldnieks” (RNP), refurbishment typically involves comprehensive measures. These include wall and attic floor insulation, foundation and cellar roof insulation, PVC window installation, external door replacement, and upgrades to heating and ventilation systems. For instance, one recent comprehensive renovation in 2023 serves as a benchmark for the expected costs and savings. The expected energy savings are approximately

30,000 EUR per building per year, highlighting the financial benefits of the renovation. This, combined with the funding from grants and municipal support, makes the investment more viable. The overall financial planning includes consideration of these savings, the funding structure, and the long-term benefits of reduced energy consumption.

Operating and Maintenance Costs: the annual operating and maintenance costs before deep renovation were €22,478 per building, which is expected to decrease to €11,238 after renovation. These costs cover general upkeep and repairs of the building and its systems. The depreciation rates for energy-efficient technologies have not been specified in detail, but the typical life cycle of these technologies is considered in the financial planning. The fixed expenses for operating and maintaining the equipment are part of the ongoing costs, although specific amounts are not detailed. The interest rate on any debt or mortgage associated with these renovations is 5% fixed.

Revenues and Taxes: energy savings are projected to generate approximately €49,000 annually per building, given the current heating tariff. While specific details on rent and tax implications for these projects are not provided, these savings constitute a significant portion of the revenue following renovation. Each building has 24 apartments, and the approximate property tax is €480. The average cadastral value of each apartment is €10,000. The initial deposit required is €5,000. The VAT rate applicable to the project is 21%.

Funding and Debt: the financing strategy for these renovations relies on a combination of grants and municipal support. ALTUM provides a grant covering 49% of the costs (excluding VAT), which amounts to €95,400, reducing the net investment costs to €222,640. Additionally, the Riga municipality offers support schemes funding up to 50% of energy efficiency measures, capped at €50,000. Loan and external financing is considered to cover the funding gap for implementing the EE interventions, with monthly payments for the remaining amount being €1,262.22 over a loan term of 20 years at an interest rate of 3.5% per year.

Market Value of the building and energy poverty: post-renovation, buildings in Riga can expect significant energy savings, reducing annual energy consumption from approximately 223 kWh/m² to around 100 kWh/m², which translates to a total annual energy consumption of about 168 MWh per building. This represents a 60% decrease in energy consumption. The market value of these buildings is likely to increase by at least 40% due to improved energy efficiency and living conditions, although specific market values are not provided. Energy poverty is a critical concern in Riga, with a principle that "Residents do not pay more after energy retrofits" guiding renovation projects. This is essential since energy poverty affects a significant portion of the population, with the expectation that renovations should not increase the financial burden on residents. Riga Energy Agency for the

Āgenskalna Priedes district have provided detailed financial data on the investment costs, and the potential energy savings resulting from the building renovations. Before the renovation, the building's energy consumption for heating was 200 kWh/m² per year, with no energy used for hot water. After the renovation, the heating consumption is projected to drop to 100 kWh/m² per year, while the hot water consumption remains unchanged at 0 kWh/m² per year. In terms of total energy consumption, the building used 200 MWh per year before the renovation and is expected to use 100 MWh per year after the renovation.

Possible financial solutions and steps for evaluating them

Based on the information provided by Riga Energy Agency for the Āgenskalna Priedes district, we have identified key factors to consider when developing the most appropriate Public-Private Partnership (PPP) contract for Latvia.

- The social housing stock is fully owned by the social housing company. This ownership structure simplifies the management and implementation of energy efficiency (EE) renovations, as there are no private owners involved in the decision-making process.
- Tenants in these social housing units will benefit directly from all energy savings generated by the proposed EE renovations. This arrangement aims to lower their energy costs and enhance their overall living conditions.
- The government will see benefits in the form of reduced CO₂ emissions, supporting Latvia's environmental goals and contributing to its sustainability commitments.

The financial solutions which will be analysed are:

1. Guaranteed savings: in Latvia the social housing company will cover the initial investment costs through savings, grants, crowdfunding and funding institutions, while the ESCO is responsible for the installation, maintenance and operation costs of the EE interventions. The social housing company is guaranteed a minimum level of energy savings equal to the cost of financing the EE interventions. If the annual energy savings are below the minimum guaranteed level the ESCO company pays the difference to the social housing company, however when the annual energy savings are higher than the minimum guaranteed level the social housing company receives the minimum guaranteed savings plus 20% of the difference between the annual energy savings and the minimum guaranteed level. Usually the duration of this contract is 20 years, and the financial and technical risks are covered by the ESCO.
2. Shared savings: the ESCO is responsible for funding the EE intervention and the operating and maintenance costs while the social housing company provides the capital asset. The ESCO is guaranteed a minimum level of energy savings equal to its annual costs. If the annual energy savings are below the minimum guaranteed level, the ESCO will receive all the energy

savings and the social housing company receives 0. In the case the annual energy savings are higher than the minimum guaranteed for the ESCO, the ESCO will receive the minimum guaranteed level of energy savings + 60% of the difference between the annual energy savings and the guaranteed minimum energy savings, while the social housing company receives the rest. The financial risk is covered by the ESCO, and the duration of these contracts are usually between 20-25 years.

3. Direct credit line: the Social housing company is responsible for funding the EE project, and covering the maintenance and operating costs of implementing the EE interventions. The financial risk and technical risk are covered by the Social housing company.
4. Energy supply contracts: the social housing company and the ESCO both cover the investment costs of the EE renovation project usually at a rate of 10%-50% for the social housing company. No party is guaranteed a minimum energy savings level, and the annual energy savings are divided according to the percentage covered by each party. The financial risk and technical risk are also shared between the parties according to the percentage of initial investments covered by each party.

2.2.4 Social

Health and Safety Measures on site

Health and safety in Latvia are governed by several key regulations designed to ensure the safety and well-being of workers and the public. The primary laws include the Labour Protection Law, which sets the framework for occupational health and safety, and various regulations that specify detailed requirements for workplace safety.

- **Risk Assessment and Prevention:** Employers are required to conduct regular risk assessments to identify potential hazards and implement preventive measures to mitigate risks. This includes ensuring the safety of workplace design, equipment, and operations.
- **Safety Training and Communication:** Employers must provide safety training and clear instructions to employees. This includes training on the safe use of work equipment, emergency procedures, and general workplace safety practices.
- **Provision of Protective Equipment:** Necessary protective equipment must be provided to employees and maintained in good condition to ensure their safety while performing job tasks.
- **Emergency Preparedness:** Employers are responsible for establishing and communicating emergency procedures, including fire safety and evacuation plans, to ensure employees are prepared for emergencies.

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- **Workplace and Equipment Safety:** Regulations require that workplaces and work equipment meet specific safety standards. Regular inspections and maintenance are necessary to ensure ongoing compliance and safety.
- **Supervision and Incident Reporting:** Construction sites and other high-risk workplaces must have designated supervisors to oversee safety compliance. Any accidents or safety incidents must be reported and investigated to prevent future occurrences.
- **Health Impact Assessment:** Latvian regulations require an assessment of possible health impacts during construction projects. Measures must be taken to limit dust and noise, ensuring they do not adversely affect workers and the public
- **Dust Control:** Employers must implement measures to control dust emissions during construction activities. This includes using methods such as water spraying, covering materials that generate dust, and employing dust extraction systems.
- **Noise Limitation:** Regulations set limits on acceptable noise levels generated by construction activities. Employers are required to use noise reduction measures such as barriers, silencers, and scheduling noisy tasks during designated hours to minimise disturbance to nearby residents and workers.

These measures aim to create a safe working environment by emphasising prevention, training, and continuous improvement. Compliance with these regulations is enforced by the State Labour Inspectorate, which conducts inspections and imposes penalties for violations.

Social engagement & social innovation actions in Herning Denmark

In Riga, Latvia, the social engagement and innovation activities are designed to empower residents and foster community cohesion while promoting sustainability. The awareness phase, launched in mid-2023, used neighborhood festivities as a platform to build connections among residents and gather insights into their needs and priorities. This creative approach featured interactive workshops and the rollout of tailored support services to introduce concepts of energy efficiency and sustainable living in a welcoming and accessible manner.

The design phase, running from late 2023 to mid-2024, took a participatory approach with a series of workshops, meetings, and seminars to educate residents about the intricacies of the renovation process. Topics included co-financing options, energy-saving strategies, and the broader environmental and economic benefits of sustainability initiatives. A key highlight was the provision of individual consultations, offering personalized guidance to ensure residents understood their role and opportunities within the project. During the renovation works phase, planned for mid-2025 to early 2026, the focus will shift to maintaining transparency and collecting continuous feedback. Questionnaires will capture residents' opinions and suggestions, while visual documentation through photos and videos will share progress, fostering trust and celebrating milestones. Residents

will remain actively involved in decision-making, particularly concerning co-designing building facades, green spaces, and internal renovations, ensuring outcomes reflect their preferences and priorities.

Post-renovation, the project will focus on evaluating and expanding its impact. A feasibility study in 2027 will explore ways to replicate successful strategies across other neighborhoods, potentially scaling up the benefits. This forward-looking approach underscores the project's commitment to long-term sustainability and innovation. Throughout the timeline, the project emphasizes continuous social engagement to deepen trust, promote social acceptance, and strengthen community bonds. By blending participatory governance with creative and educational activities, the initiative not only empowers residents with financial and technical knowledge but also fosters a sense of ownership and pride in the transformation of their neighborhood.

2.2.5 Environmental

Waste management

In Latvia, construction waste management is governed by strict regulations outlined in the Environmental Protection Law and Waste Management Law. Construction waste must be disposed of through certified waste management companies authorised to handle such materials. Each transfer of construction waste must be precisely documented and registered in the BRAPUS system (Būvniecības atkritumu pārvaldības un uzskaites sistēma).

BRAPUS is the Construction Waste Management and Accounting System in Latvia. It is a centralised electronic platform designed to monitor and manage the disposal and handling of construction waste throughout the country. BRAPUS tracks each transfer of construction waste from its generation to its final disposal or reuse, ensuring that all transactions comply with legal requirements and environmental standards. Compliance with BRAPUS regulations helps Latvia achieve its environmental goals by promoting efficient resource use and reducing the environmental impact of construction activities.

While reuse of construction waste is encouraged for sustainability, it is not mandatory unless specified in the contract by the contracting entity. These measures aim to promote responsible waste management practices and minimise the environmental impact of construction activities across Latvia.

Carbon management of site activities (if any)

In the current stage of the project, none of the pilot programs have incorporated carbon management activities. This means that while the pilots are making significant strides in areas such

as energy efficiency and social housing management, they have not yet addressed the critical issue of carbon emissions. Carbon management is a key component of sustainable development and environmental stewardship, and its absence in the pilot programs is a gap that needs to be addressed in future iterations. Incorporating carbon management strategies would not only enhance the environmental impact of the SUPERSHINE solutions but also align the project more closely with global sustainability goals.

Biodiversity impact of the implementations

Retrofit interventions can have significant impacts on biodiversity. These impacts can be both positive and negative, depending on the specific interventions and how they are implemented. Negative impacts can occur when retrofitting activities disrupt existing habitats. For example, retrofitting buildings can sometimes lead to the loss of nesting sites for birds and bats. In addition, the installation of new technologies can potentially disrupt local ecosystems, particularly if they involve significant changes to the landscape or the introduction of non-native species.

On the other hand, retrofit interventions can also have positive impacts on biodiversity. For instance, energy-efficient retrofits can help mitigate climate change, which in turn can benefit biodiversity by reducing habitat loss and other impacts associated with global warming. The impacts of retrofit interventions on biodiversity can vary significantly between different countries, due to differences in local ecosystems, species, and environmental regulations.

In Latvia, the country is home to a diverse range of species, including many that are endangered. Therefore, retrofit interventions need to be carefully planned and implemented to avoid harming these species. The country has been focusing on improving the protection of forest and grassland habitats and limiting the spread of invasive species.

2.3 Italy

2.3.1 Technical Specifications

Boito buildings 1-8 in Trieste will be demolished and rebuilt by ATER Trieste. old building built in 1951, each building currently has 16 apartments with a density of 2.5 people per apartment, which after reconstruction will be 8 apartments and 3.5 people per apartment. The old building has a total area of 7,202 m² and an energy rating of Class G. The envelope surface is 200 m² and the total

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building surface is 1,600 m². It does not have a building passport or Environmental Product Declaration.

The new building in the Boito district of Trieste, Italy, will retain the area of 7,202 m² and will be oriented 30° south. The envelope will be 200 m², with exterior plaster walls, thermal insulation, hollow brick, and interior plaster, with a thermal performance of 0.25 W/m² K. Each apartment will average 75 m². The proposed energy systems will include central heating, photovoltaic and solar energy, central hot water, central ventilation, central air conditioning and 5% LED lighting.

The new apartments will be assigned to a community composed of: 13% immigrants, 21% over 65 years old, and 34% families with children, with incomes below 15,000 euros. The complex is in an area similar to other ERP, with access to schools, sports facilities, a church, and shopping centers. Support services such as new technologies, energy savings, and waste management are suggested. The district could be included in the Habitat Microaree program. Additionally, there is a nearby industrial park and good internet connectivity. There is currently no energy community, but the complex is suitable for its creation, which could combat energy poverty.

The renovation project, owned by ATER Trieste and built in 1951, involves its demolition and reconstruction to improve energy efficiency and comfort. Initially with 16 apartments each, the buildings will now house 8 apartments per building. The new structures will have an A2 energy rating, walls with 0.45 m thick thermal insulation and a U-value of 0.25 W/m²K, and green roofs with a U-value of 0.22 W/m²K. The energy systems will include central gas and electricity heating, mechanical ventilation with heat recovery, and a photovoltaic system on the roof. Annual consumption is estimated at 16,200 kWh of electricity and 15,298 kWh of natural gas.

As a means to develop this renovation intervention, this district is assigned to the "Habitat Microaree" program, which aims to promote well-being and social cohesion in Trieste, implemented since 1998 through a collaboration between the Comune di Trieste, the local health company, and ATER.

Post-reconstruction consumption is expected to be 16,200 kWh/year in electricity, 15,298 kWh/year in natural gas, and 2,190,000 liters/year in water consumption. The reconstruction will focus on improving energy efficiency through sustainable building renovation and the integration of renewable energy sources, with the goal of achieving significant energy savings.

2.3.2 Legal

Management structure of the implementations

In managing interventions under DL 36/2023 “Codice Contratti”, Ater follows a structured approach involving both internal teams and external professionals. The design phase is overseen by Ater's internal work team in collaboration with external experts, chosen through a public procurement process that includes issuing a public call for tenders. This process allows interested parties to submit bids based on criteria such as qualifications, experience of team members, proposed methodologies, and cost of services. A dedicated Director of Internal Works at Ater ensures coordination and efficiency within the organisation. External Security Coordinators and testing teams are selected through this process to maintain safety standards and verify the effectiveness of implemented measures. This comprehensive strategy ensures that interventions are precisely planned, executed, and monitored to achieve optimal outcomes in enhancing housing conditions and community well-being.

Procurement processes, selection of contractors

The "DL 36/2023 Codice Contratti" is a significant legislative reform in Italy that governs public procurement and contracts. This new code, enacted on March 31, 2023, introduces various changes aimed at streamlining procedures and increasing transparency in public contracting. The goal of DL

Operating and Maintenance Costs: Annual operating and maintenance costs for the refurbished buildings are projected to be €20,390. Fixed annual expenditures to maintain equipment are €6,250, while other miscellaneous costs add up to €4,560. The specific depreciation rates for the renovated components are not provided, but the overall expected life cycle of the technologies is specified without exact values.

Revenues and Taxes: Expected revenues from the refurbished buildings are €16,800 annually. Additional revenues from other sources amount to €10,625. The tax rate on rents collected from these social housing buildings is set at 12%, with an identical default rate for rents. There are no tax incentives provided for carrying out the energy efficiency refurbishments. The vacancy rate for these buildings is projected to be 0%.

Funding and Debt: The funding structure involves national grants covering 85% of the costs, and private savings accounting for the remaining 15%. No EU grants or loans from financial institutions are indicated. The interest rate on any existing debt or mortgage is not specified, but the buildings' equity and expected market value post-refurbishment are not explicitly detailed.

Market Value of the Building and Energy Poverty: The expected market value of the buildings prior to EE interventions is €16,500,000. The average yearly expenditure on energy for current residents was €6,400 in 2022, representing 40% of their total yearly income. About 60% of households are unable to keep their homes adequately warm, highlighting a severe energy poverty issue.

Possible financial solutions and steps for evaluating them

Based on the information provided by ATER-Trieste for the Boito district, we have identified key characteristics to be considered in developing the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) contracts and the crowdfunding scheme.

- The social housing stock in Italy is typically co-owned by social housing companies and private owners, which necessitates a collaborative approach for effective management and implementation of the energy efficiency (EE) renovations.
- Tenants will receive all the financial benefits from the energy savings generated by the proposed EE renovations. This direct benefit is intended to reduce their energy costs and improve their overall living conditions.
- The government will benefit from reduced CO2 emissions, aligning with national environmental goals and contributing to Italy's commitment to sustainability.

- The social housing companies in Italy are not eligible to obtain loans from financial institutions. This constraint requires tailoring innovative financing solutions that do not consider loans to fund the necessary renovations.

The financial solutions which will be analysed are as follows:

1. Guaranteed savings: Under the guaranteed savings contract in Italy, the social housing company finances the initial investment costs through savings, grants, and crowdfunding, eliminating the need for external debt financing. The ESCO (Energy Service Company) is responsible for the installation, maintenance, and operational costs of the energy efficiency (EE) interventions. This contract ensures that the social housing company achieves a minimum level of energy savings equivalent to the cost of financing the EE interventions. If the annual energy savings fall below the guaranteed minimum, the ESCO pays the difference to the social housing company. Conversely, if the annual energy savings exceed the guaranteed minimum, the social housing company receives the minimum guaranteed savings plus 20% of the additional savings. Typically, these contracts last for 20 years, with the ESCO assuming both the financial and technical risks.
2. Direct credit line: Under the direct credit line contract, the social housing company is responsible for funding the EE project and covering the maintenance and operational costs of implementing the EE interventions. In this arrangement, the financial and technical risks are borne entirely by the social housing company.

2.3.4 Social

Health and Safety Measures on site

L.D. 81/2008 refers to Legislative Decree No. 81 of April 9, 2008, in Italy, which is also known as the "Testo Unico sulla Salute e Sicurezza sul Lavoro" (Consolidated Text on Occupational Health and Safety). This decree is a comprehensive legal framework aimed at ensuring health and safety in the workplace.

- Scope: Applies to all workers sectors to protect workers health and safety.
- Employer responsibilities: Employers must assess and manage risks, implement preventive measures and ensure workers receive proper training and information.
- Risk assessment: A comprehensive risk assessment must be conducted and documented in the Risk Assessment Document (DVR- Documento di Valutazione dei Rischi).
- Worker participation: Workers have the right to participate in safety discussions and elect safety representatives.

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- Training and information: Employers must provide adequate training and information on occupational risks.
- Health surveillance: Regular health checks are required for workers exposed to specific risks, conducted by a competent doctor.
- Emergency measures: Employers must prepare emergency plans and ensure workers are trained for emergencies.
- Penalties and enforcement: Non-compliance can result in fines and imprisonment, with inspections carried out by authorities like INAIL (Istituto Nazionale per l'Assicurazione contro gli Infortuni sul Lavoro- National Institute for Insurance against Accidents at Work) .

This decree aims to create a safer and healthier work environment through comprehensive risk management, worker involvement, and strict enforcement.

Social engagement & social innovation actions in Herning Denmark

In Trieste, Italy, the engagement strategy emphasizes building energy-conscious communities and enhancing social cohesion through a participatory approach. The initiative aims to transform neighborhoods by integrating sustainability with community-driven decision-making, as well as co-creation and validation of the intended renovation . The awareness phase, beginning in early 2024, serves as the foundation for fostering community involvement. Through public events, residents are introduced to the renovation master plan and the stakeholder engagement roadmap, ensuring transparency and clarity about the project's goals and benefits. These events are designed to inspire curiosity and establish a sense of shared purpose among residents, stakeholders, and local authorities.

The design phase, running from mid to late 2024, prioritizes co-creation through workshops on key themes such as building aesthetics, green spaces, and community services. These sessions enable residents to actively shape the physical and social aspects of their living environment. A distinctive feature is the establishment of energy communities, which promote collective action and shared ownership of renewable energy solutions. Special efforts are made to include schools, local NGOs, and underrepresented groups, ensuring that diverse voices contribute to the project's vision.

During the renovation works phase, scheduled from 2025 to 2026, the focus shifts to equipping tenants with the knowledge and tools necessary to make the most of their upgraded living spaces. Training programs on energy-saving tools and new technologies empower residents to adopt sustainable practices, while regular updates—delivered through meetings, newsletters, and digital platforms—maintain trust and engagement throughout the process.

Regarding the post-renovation phase, the strategy will shift towards sustaining and amplifying project benefits. Community-building events will encourage ongoing interaction among neighbours, while sociologist-led workshops will address residents' long-term needs and satisfaction. These activities aim to reinforce the project's social and environmental impacts, ensuring residents feel empowered and connected within their community. The project's structured timeline spans from early 2024 through 2026, allowing for incremental capacity building and iterative feedback loops. This approach balances immediate engagement with long-term sustainability, transforming the renovation process into a collaborative journey. By blending participatory design with innovative energy solutions, Trieste's initiative sets a benchmark for creating resilient, energy-conscious, and socially cohesive urban communities.

2.3.5 Environmental

Waste management

In managing waste and carbon emissions under current legislation, Italy emphasises the separate transfer of special materials during demolition and their safe disposal in authorised landfills. This approach is governed by directives like the Waste Framework Directive and Italy's Environmental Code, which ensure proper recycling and environmental protection. Additionally, Italy promotes the design of nearly zero-energy buildings (NZEBS), aligning with EU standards to minimise carbon footprints and enhance energy efficiency. These measures reflect Italy's commitment to sustainable development and compliance with EU climate goals, fostering a greener and more resilient built environment for the future.

- European Directives: Italy aligns its waste management policies with EU directives, particularly the Waste Framework Directive (Directive 2008/98/EC), which sets the basic concepts and definitions related to waste management, such as recycling and recovery.
- National Legislation: The primary national legislation governing waste management in Italy is Legislative Decree No. 152/2006, also known as the Environmental Code. This decree transposes EU directives into Italian law and covers waste management, recycling, and environmental protection.
- Decree-Law No. 69/2013 (also known as the "Decreto del Fare"): Enhances procedures for the separate collection and proper disposal of construction and demolition waste,

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emphasising the need to segregate hazardous materials and ensure their safe transfer to authorised facilities.

- Regulation (EU) No.305/2011 (Construction Products Regulation- CPR): This regulation ensures that construction products, including those involved in demolition and waste, comply with EU standards for health, safety, and environmental protection.

Carbon management of site activities (if any)

The lighthouses have not yet incorporated any carbon management activities. This is an area that could be considered for future iterations of the project, as managing carbon emissions is a crucial aspect of environmental sustainability. It's important to note that the inclusion of carbon management strategies would enhance the environmental impact of the SUPERSHINE solutions and align the project more closely with global sustainability goals.

Biodiversity impact of the implementations

Italy is among the European countries richest in biodiversity. It has the highest number and density of both animal and plant species within the European Union. This rich biodiversity is largely due to its range of biogeographic regions, which provide differences in climate, topography, and geology. Italy is estimated to include over 58,000 faunal species and over 6,700 vascular plant species. The country has a high incidence of endemic species, with around 30% of animal species and 15% of vascular plants species being endemic. However, Italy's biodiversity is under threat due to factors such as urbanisation. The Italian peninsula represents a crucial crossroad in the migration pathways of several migratory animals, both marine and avian species. The variety of biogeographical conditions that can be found throughout Italy continually lead populations and species to differentiate.

3. Data collection for Life Cycle Analysis

This table represents which information collected from the surveys will be represented in the calculations of the LCA from the original list of KPIs that the literature research proposed.

Part 1 **Part 2** **Not Available**

Indicator	Required input	Denmark	Latvia	Italy
GWP	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, units...)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available
	Total non renewable annual Energy Consumption (kWh annual)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available
OZONE DEPLETION POTENTIAL	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, units...)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available
ACIDIFICATION POTENTIAL (AP)	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, units...)	Part 1	Not Available	Not Available
PHOTOCHEMICAL OXIDANT CREATION POTENTIAL	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, units...)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available

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CONSTRUCTION WASTE MANAGEMENT	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, units...)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available
WASTE REDUCTION RATE	Total estimate of waste generated in a building during use phase (Kg or tons)	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
EFFICIENCY IN WASTE DISPOSAL PROCESSES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total estimate of waste generated in a building during use phase that goes to Landfilling (Kg or tons) Total estimate of waste generated in a building during use phase that goes to Incineration (Kg or tons) Total estimate of waste generated in a building during use phase that goes to Recycling (Kg or tons) Total estimate of waste generated in a building during use phase that goes to Biomass, Composting / Reusing (Kg or tons) 	Part 2	Not Available	Not Available
		Part 2	Not Available	Not Available
		Part 2	Not Available	Not Available
		Part 2	Not Available	Not Available
LAND USE EFFICIENCY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total built area for residential use (m2) Total area for public space (m2) 	Part 1	Part 2	Not Available
IMPACT ON BIODIVERSITY	QUESTIONS TO SURVEY ON D3.3 (P96)	Part 1	Not Available	Not Available
WATER CONSUMPTION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drinkable Water consumption 	Part 1	Not Available	Not Available

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of residents (m2) 	Part 1	Part 1	
WATER RECYCLING INDEX	Answer to survey (Y/N)	Part 1	Not Available	Not Available
EUTROPHICATION POTENTIAL	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, units...)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available
RESPONSIBLE SOURCING OF MATERIALS	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, m3, units...)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available
MATERIALS LIFECYCLE ANALYSIS	Total quantity of retrofit materials (kgs,m2, m3, units...)	Part 1	Part 1	Not Available
HUMIDITY CONTROL	Humidity sensors in indoor spaces %	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
TEMPERATURE CONTROL	Temperature sensors in indoor spaces %	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
NATURE DAYLIGHT	INDOOR AIR QUALITY	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
INDOOR AIR QUALITY	Indoor sensors for measuring CO2 levels, PM2.5, total VOCs	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
NOISE LEVELS	Noise sound pressure	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available

4. Action plan for financial solutions

4.1 Strategy to support social housing associations to implement the financial solutions.

The implementation of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) and crowdfunding mechanisms will significantly enhance the financial capacity of social housing associations to cover the investment costs necessary for implementing energy efficiency refurbishment projects. These innovative funding mechanisms will bridge current existing funding gaps presented in D3.3, and D4.1, leverage private sector efficiencies, and engage communities in energy efficiency projects. The action plan for financial solutions provides a strategy that outlines the steps, processes, and considerations necessary for FaellsBo, Ater housing association and REA to successfully implement PPP and crowdfunding contracts. This action plan involves providing technical assistance, facilitating stakeholder engagement, offering financial advisory services, and ensuring regulatory compliance. The following comprehensive strategy outlines how the SUPERSHINE project will support these efforts.

Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) funding contracts

Capacity building:

SUPERSHINE will organise workshops tailored to each lighthouse country, building the capacity of social housing associations to understand and implement PPPs. These sessions will cover the basics of PPPs, their benefits and challenges, detailed steps for structuring PPP contracts, risk management and allocation strategies, and the regulatory requirements specific to SUPERSHINE lighthouses and the EU. Additionally, a platform for sharing best practices, case studies, and lessons learned from successful PPP projects within the SUPERSHINE lighthouse countries and internationally will be established. This platform will include online forums, regular webinars featuring PPP and energy-efficient renovations, and access to all the relevant documents and templates.

Technical Assistance:

SUPERSHINE will provide technical assistance to social housing associations in identifying suitable PPPs for implementing the EE interventions. This includes conducting initial assessments to identify high-potential EE interventions and assisting in the preparation of detailed financial feasibility studies. Support will also be provided in the development of comprehensive PPP contracts. This

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involves providing templates and guidelines for contract drafting, offering expert review and feedback on draft contracts, and ensuring contracts include clear definitions of roles, responsibilities, performance metrics, and risk-sharing mechanisms.

Financial advisory services:

SUPERSHINE will assist social housing associations in structuring financial models that are attractive to private investors. This includes developing financial projections and cash flow analyses, identifying potential sources of financing, and advising on the use of government guarantees and other risk mitigation instruments. To support partner identification and engagement, SUPERSHINE will create a database of potential private sector partners, facilitate matchmaking events, and assist in evaluating partners based on financial stability, technical expertise, and commitment to sustainability.

Crowdfunding

Capacity building and training:

SUPERSHINE will organise specialised workshops focused on crowdfunding strategies and platforms. These workshops will cover the introduction to various crowdfunding models, steps for planning and launching a successful crowdfunding campaign, and strategies for engaging the community and building a supporter base. Social housing associations will also have access to resources such as guides on crowdfunding best practices, case studies of successful campaigns, and expert advice.

Technical Assistance:

SUPERSHINE will assist social housing associations in planning their campaigns. This involves helping to set realistic funding goals, crafting compelling campaign stories, developing attractive rewards, and creating comprehensive marketing plans that utilise social media, email campaigns, and local events. SUPERSHINE will also provide ongoing support throughout the campaign, including monitoring performance, responding to feedback, and maintaining engagement.

Financial advisory services:

SUPERSHINE will guide social housing associations in selecting the most suitable crowdfunding platforms. This involves evaluating different platforms based on their focus, user base, support services, and fee structures, and recommending platforms that specialise in social and

environmental projects. SUPERSHINE will also provide ongoing support throughout the campaign, including monitoring performance, responding to feedback, and maintaining engagement.

Regulatory and Legal Compliance:

SUPERSHINE will guide social housing associations through the complex regulatory and legal landscape. This includes providing information on relevant Italian and EU regulations, assisting in securing necessary permits and approvals, and advising on compliance with public procurement laws and EU state aid rules. Additionally, SUPERSHINE will develop a robust monitoring and evaluation framework to ensure compliance and performance throughout the project lifecycle. This involves setting up Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), conducting regular audits and reviews, and implementing corrective actions as needed.

4.2 KPIs for implementation of financial solutions

Number of Energy-Efficient interventions Completed: This KPI tracks the number of energy-efficient renovations successfully financed and completed through crowdfunding and PPPs.

- **Formula:** Total number of completed energy-efficient interventions.
- **Data Needed:**
 - Project completion certificates.
 - Renovation project records.
- **Frequency:** Quarterly.
- **Source of Data:** Project management offices of social housing associations, progress reports from contractors.
- **Usage:** Tracking the number of completed renovations helps measure the tangible outcomes of financing efforts. A high number of completed projects indicates effective use of funds and successful implementation of energy-efficient renovations.

ROI on PPPs: This KPI measures the return on investment for projects funded through PPPs, reflecting the financial performance of these investments.

Data Needed:

- Financial statements showing costs and revenues.
- Detailed records of investments and profits.

Frequency: Annually.

Source of Data: Financial departments of social housing associations, reports from private partners.

Usage: Monitoring ROI helps assess the financial viability and success of PPP-funded projects. Positive ROI indicates profitable investments.

Energy Savings Achieved: This KPI evaluates the reduction in energy consumption as a result of funded renovation projects, reflecting the impact on energy efficiency.

- **Data Needed:**
 - Energy consumption data before and after renovation.
 - Energy bills and usage records.
- **Frequency:** Annually.
- **Source of Data:** energy audits, and reports from housing associations.
- **Usage:** Monitoring energy savings helps quantify the environmental benefits of renovation projects. Significant energy savings demonstrate the effectiveness of funded projects in improving energy efficiency.

Total Funds Raised Through PPPs and Crowdfunding: This KPI quantifies the overall financial resources mobilized through PPPs and crowdfunding for social housing renovations.

- **Data Needed:**
 - Records of funds raised through PPPs.
 - Crowdfunding platform reports.
 - Bank statements showing fund transfers.
- **Frequency:** Quarterly.
- **Source of Data:** Financial departments of social housing associations, crowdfunding platforms, private and public partners.
- **Usage:** Monitoring this KPI provides a comprehensive view of the financial inflows supporting the social housing energy efficiency project. It highlights the financial capacity being built through PPPs and crowdfunding.

Crowdfunding Campaign Success Rate: This KPI measures the percentage of crowdfunding campaigns that reach their funding goals, reflecting the ability to mobilize community financial support for social housing projects.

- **Data Needed:**
 - Campaign funding goals.

- Amount raised for each campaign.
- Campaign status (successful or not).
- **Frequency:** Monthly.
- **Source of Data:** Crowdfunding platform.
- **Usage:** Tracking this KPI helps evaluate the effectiveness of the adopted crowdfunding strategy. A high success rate indicates strong community engagement and effective campaign management.

Crowdfunding Participation Rate: This KPI tracks the number of individuals contributing to crowdfunding campaigns for social housing projects, reflecting community engagement and support.

- **Data Needed:**
 - Contributor data from crowdfunding platforms.
 - Campaign records showing number of contributors.
- **Frequency:** Monthly.
- **Source of Data:** Crowdfunding platforms, financial reports from housing associations.
- **Usage:** This KPI helps assess the level of community involvement in crowdfunding efforts. A high participation rate indicates strong community support and effective outreach.

Growth in Crowdfunding Contributions: This KPI monitors the year-over-year increase in funds raised through crowdfunding campaigns for social housing.

- **Data Needed:**
 - Annual crowdfunding campaign financial records.
- **Frequency:** Annually.
- **Source of Data:** Crowdfunding platform, financial reports from housing associations.
- **Usage:** Monitoring growth in contributions helps assess the effectiveness of crowdfunding efforts over time. Consistent growth indicates increasing community engagement and successful campaign strategies.

4.3 Methodology for ranking PPPs and crowdfunding schemes

Through a comprehensive financial analysis we analyse the economic viability of the tailored PPP and crowdfunding schemes using a bottom-up model analysis. Firstly, we model the expected energy savings from each proposed intervention for each building using the SUPER-i energy-saving model. This step is crucial in identifying the potential energy efficiency gains that can be achieved

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through various measures. Next, we use a powerful stochastic volatility model to simulate future values for several key variables. These include the energy market bid price, inflation rate, interest rate on debt, property value growth rate, rent growth rate, and the default rate on rent. Additionally, we incorporate socio-economic variables necessary for calculating the social discount rate, such as the employment rate in the specific region (or national level as a proxy), national level income growth rate specific to each region (or national level as a proxy), earning rate on personal savings (private savings/consumption) at the national level, corporate taxes, private investment, private consumption, and government spending. In the third step, we measure the social discount rate using the weighted average method (WAM) with the following socio-economic variables: SRTP, a measure of private savings/consumption, and SOC, a measure of private investment. Furthermore, we analyse the financial and socio-economic impact of the interventions for each building separately. This analysis is based on the findings from the energy savings analysis, the simulated financial variables, and the social discount rate. We utilise various financial metrics including Return on Investment (ROI), Net Cash Flow (NCF), Net Present Value (NPV) of the project and the risk-adjusted extra return. In the fifth step, we replicate this process at the building block level, and then at the district level in the sixth step. This will ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the financial and socio-economic impacts across different scales of implementation. Next, we compare our findings against investing in a benchmark, such as the S&P 500 index, to assess the relative performance of the proposed interventions.

Finally, we rank the PPP and crowdfunding schemes from most suitable funding solution to least suitable funding solution based on the risk-adjusted extra returns metric for each involved stakeholder in the EE renovation project.

5. Action Plan for the One Stop Shop

The SUPERSHINE One-Stop-Shop (OSS) Action Plan is designed to streamline the process of integrated district renovation. Here's a detailed action plan based on the provided information:

- **User Classification**

A questionnaire will be used to classify users based on their characteristics, needs, and interests. This will ensure that the services provided by the OSS are tailored to meet the specific needs of each user.

- **Business Model:**

The OSS will operate based on a business model that ensures its sustainability and effectiveness. More details about this model can be found in the deliverable.

- **Examples of Possible Outputs:**

The OSS will provide examples of possible outputs from the SUPERSHINE pilots in a simple and intuitive way. These examples will serve as a guide for users and will be linked to the respective Lighthouse districts.

- **Surveys:**

Links to surveys will be provided, along with explanations and instructions on how to fill them. These surveys will help gather valuable feedback from users, which can be used to improve the services provided by the OSS.

- **Technical, Financial, Environmental, and Social Sections:**

The OSS will include sections dedicated to technical, financial, environmental, and social aspects. Each section will contain general information, including relevant regulations at the EU and country level, as well as specific outputs.

- **Coordination and Integration:**

The OSS will coordinate existing market actors, including suppliers and innovative SMEs, and ensure that all services are offered to social housing managers and residents. It will also interact with local businesses and services to harmonise energy efficiency refurbishment at the district level.

- **Single-Entry Point:**

The OSS will function as a single-entry point, managing the information flow between the governmental and business partners delivering the services and the potential customers. It will centralise customers' needs and assign tasks/orders to the corresponding partners.

- **IT Requirements:**

The OSS will require a website, server, domain, and other IT infrastructure for its operation. The interface will be web-based and accessible via API.

The SUPERSHINE OSS aims to offer a full renovation package with guaranteed energy savings to social housing residents and managers. It will provide a customer-focused platform that delivers the best customised solution based on customers' requests and needs. The revenue streams from the commercial deployment of the SUPERSHINE platform will come from various sources and work on a service-based scheme, similar to the "Netflix" model. The costs related to platform maintenance and annual fees are expected to impact less than 60% of revenues in a multiannual budget scenario, as stated in the business plan. This action plan will guide the implementation of the OSS, ensuring it effectively meets the needs of its users and contributes to the overall goals of the SUPERSHINE project.

6. Conclusions

The definition of the action plan has been instrumental in guiding the project towards its goals. It has effectively incorporated the insights from the feasibility studies and KPI definition, and has guided the implementation of the solutions and technologies. The strategies developed are meant to overcome the unique barriers in each district and will demonstrate the adaptability of the action plan. The successful initial technology implementations will further validate the effectiveness of the action plan. This document has thoroughly examined the technical requirements needed before retrofit interventions can take place in the lighthouse districts, including the analysis of the current state of the districts and the technical specifications necessary for the implementation of the SUPERSHINE solutions.

The document has addressed the importance of data collection for conducting both the life cycle analysis and the financial analysis. The data collection process will be continuously updated using the latest inputs from both the lighthouse districts and the fellow cities.

The case of Herning and the FællesBo district shows that making big improvements in sustainability and energy efficiency is possible by using new technologies and upgrading old infrastructure. These efforts help reduce carbon emissions and improve the quality of life for residents, leading to more inclusive and resilient urban development. Cooperation between local authorities, residents, and private partners is essential to overcome challenges and get the most out of these projects. The successful use of biomass heating, LED lighting, and solar panels has greatly reduced energy consumption, showing the practical benefits of these changes. Also, involving the community in planning and execution ensures the solutions meet the specific needs of the area, creating a sense of ownership and teamwork among residents. Including thorough risk and safety management practices, following environmental protection laws, and working to enhance biodiversity further highlights the project's comprehensive approach.

One Stop Shop Action Plan: The development of an action plan for the One Stop Shop follows up on the project commitment to providing a comprehensive service platform for social housing residents and managers. As described, it will include full renovation packages with guaranteed energy savings.

In Denmark, FællesBo Social Housing Company manages building renovations through a tender process, while direct contracts are used for energy management, recycling, and PV activities under SUPERSHINE, ensuring efficient risk and safety management. Health and safety on site follows the Danish Working Environment Act, and waste is managed under the Danish Environmental Protection Act, promoting biodiversity through sustainable practices. In Italy, Ater follows DL

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36/2023 Codice Contratti for procurement, with detailed risk management plans and a phased implementation approach, complying with L.D. 81/2008 for health and safety and stringent waste management laws aligned with EU standards. Latvia's renovation projects, often managed by SIA "Rīgas namu pārvaldnieks," involve detailed procurement and risk management overseen by various stakeholders. Health and safety regulations ensure comprehensive risk assessments and training, while waste management is monitored through the BRAPUS system. Biodiversity impacts are managed to promote sustainability, though none of the countries have incorporated carbon management in their current stages.

Regarding the Social Engagement & Social Innovation Actions, the described engagement strategies in Riga, Herning, and Trieste demonstrate how local contexts, social structures, and specific challenges are addressed through participatory processes, shaped according to the specific identities of the three communities. In Riga, capacity-building and co-creation workshops (both physical and digital, through the Tandems platform specifically built by REA and its partner for this purpose), as well as validation sessions and consultations, are ensuring residents to shape the renovation process, reinforcing their sense of ownership, while Herning's tenant democracy model is empowering residents to guide decision-making. Trieste focuses on co-designing customised for different target groups, not only for buildings but also community services and common spaces and green areas to enhance social cohesion and open the social housing district to the surrounding communities.

The project's phased approach—from awareness to post-renovation—ensures ongoing community involvement at every stage. By using workshops, meetings, and training sessions, the project fosters trust and encourages active participation, leading to increased social acceptance of energy-efficient solutions. The use of key performance indicators (KPIs) helps assess the impact of these actions and provides a framework for continuous improvement.

Ultimately, the SUPERSHINE project showcases how socially inclusive and participatory approaches to urban renovation can drive both environmental and social transformation. The lessons learned in these lighthouse cities will guide future initiatives, promoting a sustainable and community-centered model of urban renewal.

The SUPERSHINE project in Denmark, Italy, and Latvia will offer a comprehensive action plan for implementing innovative financial solutions such as PPPs and crowdfunding. This action plan aims to strengthen the financial capacity of social housing associations to undertake energy efficiency refurbishments. The strategy provides extensive support for navigating and implementing PPP and crowdfunding contracts, including technical assistance to identify suitable energy efficiency

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interventions and financial advisory services to develop attractive financial models. Key performance indicators (KPIs) will be established to monitor the effectiveness of PPP and crowdfunding contracts, including the number of energy-efficient interventions completed, ROI on PPPs, energy savings achieved, total funds raised, crowdfunding campaign success rate, participation rate, and growth in contributions. This multifaceted approach ensures the SUPERSHINE project secures necessary funding, effectively engages stakeholders, and tracks performance to guarantee successful energy efficiency renovations in social housing.